

Impact of The Economic Crisis In Pakistan

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Abstract

This study discusses the state of the economy of Pakistan and the impact of the same on future scenarios relevant to the stability of Pakistan as a country by analysing some of the economic indicators, the factors helping sustain the economy, the recent challenges faced, as well as the pressures on the Pakistani economy that are foreseen based on the current commitments in order to examine the stability of Pakistan and the resultant implications for India. The study also discusses how the economic crisis is affected by the management of Pakistan beyond just the economy per se.

Keywords Pakistan, Economy, India, Strategy

Introduction The economic situation in Pakistan has been worrying. Many financial indicators have seen a downward trend. Pakistan's economy faced a contraction in FY23, after two consecutive years of better growth. Despite the gross domestic product (GDP) growing by 6.1% in FY22 and 5.8% in FY21, it shrank by 0.2% in FY23.[1] [2]. Despite some improvement of current account balance, the external account pressure on the foreign exchange markets resulted in depreciation of PKR/USD exchange rate by 27.8% last year. The average inflation rate in Pakistan has reduced to 26% in FY24 from around 29% in FY23 however it is still soaring as compared to around 11.0% in the period before that. This high level of headline inflation is emanating from weaker exchange rate, supply disruptions created by flood damages and increased prices of electricity and fuel. The prolonged Russia-Ukraine conflict, after-effects of pandemic, and climate change have adversely disrupted international energy and food markets.[3]The country's sources of revenues lie thin on the ground whereas non-development expenditures remain high, certainly a recipe for financial disaster and economic pains. Fiscal deficit is also expected to remain. All this when looked holistically gives a very grim economic picture in the short to medium term.

Objective of study

The objectives of this study are: -

1. To probe the trajectory of the current economic crisis in Pakistan
2. To analyse the possibilities of future economic path
3. To examine the likely implications for the future stability of Pakistan
4. To study the impact of Pakistan's economic tribulations on Indian concerns and policies going forward

Review of Literature

As per the World Bank's Pakistan Development Update Report in recent years, long-standing structural challenges pose risks to Pakistan's sustained growth[4] and sustained reform commitment is needed to overcome Pakistan's Economic Crisis.[5] Reduction in poverty has slowed down and economic growth remains volatile and sluggish amid all the shocks faced. The new government faces macroeconomic challenges and economic growth is expected to remain subdued.

Methodology The study is based on secondary data and is composed of analysis from various documents and data available in the public domain, reports published by Government of Pakistan and various international agencies, as well as academic publications and reports of research institutes.

Analysis

In the past, studies and analyst views echoed the sentiment that Pakistan is a failed state, inexorably heading towards chaos and possible breakup. While Pakistan so far has proved the doomsday prophecies wrong, their internal security crises have further worsened the economic health of the country and have come at a time when Pakistan’s economy is in really bad shape. While the Pakistani leadership is busy seeking waiver of foreign debts, domestically it faces high energy prices and acute power shortages which are affecting the country’s manufacturing sectors while the disturbed security situation is hampering foreign investments. Pakistan has been steadily burdened with increasing national debt. In 1999, the debt stood at ~Rs. 3.06 trillion (US\$11 billion) and rose to ~Rs. 62.5 trillion (US\$220 billion) by 2022. Although there was an average increase of 14% per year in debt, the growth rate of GDP was only around 3% per year. Thus, Pakistan accumulated an unsustainable and ever-growing burden of debt. In 2022-2023, Pakistan was obligated to service a debt of nearly Rs. 5.2 trillion which is more than the whole federal revenue for the year. Moreover, the impact of the 2022 series of crises - political unrest, an economic crisis, and devastating floods as well as the impact of Russia’s war in Ukraine, on fuel and food prices is significant. Low foreign reserves, high inflation and currency decline also threaten the financial stability of the country. A closer analysis of the country’s broad contours demonstrates that the economic crisis is more about the management of Pakistan than just the economy.

The relationship between the military and civilian institutions—the government, media, judiciary, civil society—has not been one of consistent hegemonic domination over the last 60 years.[6] Thirty-three years of military rule shut out any civilian independence, although even under martial law, civilian and political actors resisted military might, often at great personal cost. Even when the military gave its “permission” to hold elections it dominated almost all decisions, which ought to have been in the civilian political domain.

In 2022, it was Pakistan's economic crisis that formed the basis of a political standoff between the next Prime Minister Shehbaz Sharif and his predecessor Imran Khan, which brought about Khan's ouster. Sharif accused Khan of mishandling the country's foreign policy as well as mismanaging the economy, forcing him to step down in a no-confidence vote. The national unrest and chaos amidst this political turmoil and constitutional crisis acted as a catalyst for worsening economic conditions. In 2019, Imran Khan had tried to push through a bailout deal with the International Monetary fund (IMF). The IMF had put forward various measures such as lifting the cap on fuel prices, raising electricity prices, ramping up tax collection and making sizeable budget cuts as conditions for the deal. Khan agreed to these various reforms and conditions that actually resulted in an increase in inflation, however ultimately that bid to get help from IMF failed. In 2023, the IMF finally agreed to a \$3 billion Stand-By Arrangement for 9 months conditional upon strict implementation of reforms. Based on the performance during this arrangement, in 2024 the IMF agreed to a further agreement on a 37-month Extended Fund Facility Arrangement (EFF) of about US\$7 billion thus helping the country stave off the chances of default.[7] The current coalition government has close ties with the military and so the Pakistani Army still dominates in all important areas of decision making, leaving the professional experts playing second fiddle. Terrorism, Pakistan Taliban (TTP), Taliban takeover of Afghanistan, continuing discrimination against minorities, sectarian divide, regional factions, the continued growth in fundamentalism in all sections of society and government institutions, all foster an unstable and risky environment for the economy.

The 2022-2023 economic crisis of Pakistan in itself arose from the culmination of a number of factors. Political instability, high international fuel and commodity prices, and bludgeoning trade deficit exerted immense pressure on foreign exchange reserves resulting in significant depreciation of KPR against USD which in turn contributed towards high inflation. Food, gas and oil prices thus rose to exceedingly high levels. The Russian invasion of Ukraine caused this global rise in fuel prices. And the excessive external borrowings by the country over the years heightened the threat of default, causing the currency to fall and making imports more expensive.

Figure 1.1 History of Pakistan’s External Debt (Year 1947 - 2018), Source: Ministry of Finance 1947-2018

Poor governance and low productivity per capita when compared to other similar developing nations contributed to a balance of payment crisis, where the country was unable to earn enough foreign exchange to fund its consumption in terms of imports thus leading to one of Pakistan’s biggest economic crisis since its independence.

The 2022 Pakistan floods in the summer devastated the country and caused over \$30 billion dollars in economic losses, pushing the already teetering economy to its brink. By June 2022, Inflation in Pakistan rose to 21.3%, the highest since December 2008 when inflation stood at 23.3%. Pakistan then took a loan of \$2.3 billion from a Chinese consortium of banks that was credited to the central bank’s account. At the end of March 2022, the State Bank of Pakistan’s reserves stood at \$11.425bn, but they gradually tanked to an almost four-year low of \$6.715bn on 2nd December. Pakistan’s foreign exchange reserves equalled just five weeks of merchandise imports.

As inflation raged across the country and economists predicted no respite from increasing inflation, Pakistan’s Consumer price index (CPI) further jumped to 35.4%, the highest annual rate in 50 years, driven by skyrocketing costs of food, electricity, beverage, and transport. Food inflation surged to 47.1% in urban and 50.2 % in rural areas.

China lent Pakistan an additional 700 million dollars to prop up its Forex reserves. The New York based ratings agency Fitch downgraded Pak’s sovereign credit rating from CCC+ to CCC-, warning that a default could be a "real possibility".[8] Moody’s downgraded Pakistan’s rating to Caa3. The World Bank projected about 4 million Pakistani people falling below the lower middle-income (\$3.6/day) poverty, and in May 2023, Pakistan’s inflation rate reached 38%, surpassing Sri Lanka to become the highest amongst all the Asian countries.

The economic crisis had devastating impact on industries and services, with closure of textile mills leading to the loss of jobs for over five million people, the closure of manufacturing plants, shut down of car assembly plants such as those of Pak Suzuki Motors, Toyota Indus, Honda Atlas, shut down of mobile phone assembly units and the halt of operations of a number of leading companies. In February 2023, Pakistan’s largest petroleum refinery Cnergyico even faced temporary closure as the shortage of forex reserves and currency depreciation made it difficult to import crude oil.[9] Critical imports of medicines, healthcare devices and pharmaceutical raw material were stuck at ports due to delays in securing letters of credit.[10] Treatment and surgeries across the country faced delays and postponement due to severe shortage of medicines and equipment in the wake of the closure of several pharmaceutical companies due to "unaffordable cost of production".[11] In June 2023, Shell plc announced that it would exit the Pakistani market by selling its entire 77.42% stake in Shell Pakistan. Thus, reviewing the state of the Pakistani economy in the wake of the series of crises faced paints a picture of instability, lack of sustainability, hostile environment for growth and overall economic deterioration.

In light of this, the management of the budget and formulation of right economic policies becomes imperative. However, despite the strain that excessive military spending puts on the budget, Pakistan continues its trend of increasing the allocation for military expenditure year on year.

Figure 1.2 Pakistan Military Expenditure

Overall, the economy of the country is in a poor state due to its shortsighted economic policies, excessive spending on military to achieve regional parity and an elitist approach towards governance as well as the impact of devastating floods and the political and economic crises of 2022. So far, Pakistan's economy was propped up by funds from the West, ostensibly in support of the Global War on Terror in Afghanistan, as well as from Islamic brethren in Saudi Arabia and the Gulf, along with aid from China to counter India. With the retreat of the West from Afghanistan and the reluctance of Saudi Arabia to continue handing out further bailouts and interest-free loans without the implementation of strict monetary and fiscal reforms, Pakistan looks ever more towards China for aid. A quick look at the arms exports to Pakistan from China and the US shows that although the exports from the West show a declining trend, the arms exports from China trend further and further upwards. The reliance on China for aid and worsening domestic economic situation could lead to further problems in the future.

Figure 1.3 Arms exports to Pakistan

Conclusion

Pakistan's economy is currently in a fragile and vulnerable state with insufficient public resources to finance development and provide a buffer against future shocks or downturns. Economic growth is expected to underperform and remain slightly below potential over the medium term, while limited improvements in investment and exports are anticipated. With depleted policy buffers to shore up resilience, the economy remains vulnerable to any fresh domestic or external shock. Thus, one can expect the overall outlook to be vulnerable to high downside risks.

Corruption and self-serving policies catering to civilian elites and military officials plague Pakistan's economy while ignoring the needs and concerns of the vast working populace engaged in agriculture, industries or services. Maintaining patterns of the past are unlikely to lead to better outcomes, instead crucial reforms backed by a stable government is the need of the hour. Although the recent general elections in Pakistan in 2024 led to the formation of a shaky coalition, there is hope in the form of a new \$7-billion bailout deal with the International Monetary Fund.

By May 2024 Pakistan's burden of total external public debt amounted to around \$86.287 billion; thus making debt restructuring an essential need. For the time being, Pakistan may end up avoiding default with the help of the IMF help and loans from allies. However, those won't address the clear underlying malaise of the economy – and the fact that fundamental changes are needed, such as a rebalancing of production, income and expenditure in a sustainable way, to avoid default down the road. A more stable recovery of the economy is only possible by a strong and focused political leadership pushing through medium-term reforms based on enhancing competitiveness and fiscal consolidation. Pakistan needs to improve the quality of public spending and take serious measures to expand the revenue base, and ensure the payment and collection of taxes from the eligible citizens as well as increased revenue from agriculture, retail and property. It needs to implement business regulatory and trade reforms and reduce the presence of the state in the economy to increase productivity, competitiveness, and exports. It would also need to implement measures to rationalize fiscal expenditures, such as by reducing wasteful and regressive subsidy spending and mitigating the high costs and inefficiencies in the energy sector by measures like privatization of electricity distribution companies.

Chinese state media emphasizes the strengths and benefits of the China-Pakistan Economic Corridor and blames the Pakistani economic crisis on the West. China paints a picture of the Western world having 'abandoned' Pakistan, with only China as the one extending a helping hand. On the other hand, the US has expressed serious concerns about debt owed to China. Since the Gulf Arab states that have traditionally supported Pakistan are now reluctant to continue handing out further bailouts and interest-free loans without strict conditions, Pakistan increasingly sees China as its most reliable source of

aid. The deteriorating state of the domestic economy as well as the reliance on China are significant concerns with regards to the stability of Pakistan and its impact on its neighbours. This increasing Chinese influence in Pakistan is not a favourable outcome for India.

Apart from this a stagnant economy littered with goods and energy shortages is a breeding ground for unrest as well as an opportunity for the Pakistani Taliban and other terrorist groups to emerge emboldened, leading to a significant weakening of the state and its capacity to impose order. Thus, leading to escalating security risks across the border to India as well. Turbulence and instability in Pakistan would be a major destabilizing factor in the subcontinent. The possibility that India would be exposed to large-scale acts of terrorism and communal clashes cannot be ruled out. A spill-over of refugees into India due to economic stress or civil unrest is a possibility. To divert attention from the turmoil within and the weak economic outlook, the possibility of a Pakistani military venture against India cannot be ruled out. To ensure its security, India must be prepared to contend with all such possible scenarios to fend off any spill-over effects from any destabilization in Pakistan, at the same time strengthening its security apparatus and military readiness to safeguard itself against challenges emerging from an economically unstable Pakistan

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